

Smart Irrigation System with Soil Moisture Monitoring Using Arduino UNO

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KEYWORDS

IoT, automated irrigation system, soil moisture monitoring, smart agriculture

ABSTRACT

The efficient water management has become a major concern in agriculture due to increasing water scarcity and the need for sustainable farming practices. Traditional irrigation methods often depend on manual operation or fixed scheduling, which can lead to either overwatering or insufficient watering of crops. To address these limitations, this project proposes an Automated Plant Irrigation and Soil Moisture Monitoring System using IoT technology. The integration of IoT enables real time monitoring and remote access to system data through cloud platforms or mobile applications. Users can track environmental conditions and control irrigation from anywhere, enhancing convenience and decision-making capabilities. Similar IoT based systems have demonstrated improved irrigation efficiency and reduced human intervention in agriculture.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth in security requirements across residential, industrial, and public sectors has led to an increasing demand for advanced surveillance systems. Conventional surveillance methods, such as fixed CCTV cameras, are limited by their static field of view and inability to adapt to dynamic environments. These limitations reduce their effectiveness in monitoring large or complex areas, thereby creating a need for more flexible and intelligent solution[6]. Recent developments in embedded systems and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies have enabled the design of mobile surveillance platforms capable of real-time

monitoring and remote accessibility. Surveillance robots, in particular, have gained attention due to their ability to navigate through different environments while continuously capturing and transmitting data. These systems reduce human effort and enhance monitoring efficiency, especially in critical and hazardous situations [1].

The ESP32 microcontroller has emerged as a key component in such applications due to its integrated Wi-Fi capabilities, compact design, and cost-effectiveness. It allows seamless wireless communication and supports real-time video streaming when integrated with camera modules. Web-based and

mobile-controlled surveillance systems using ESP32 have demonstrated effective remote operation and user-friendly accessibility, making them suitable for modern security applications [2].

Mobile surveillance robots equipped with ESP32-CAM modules and wireless control mechanisms provide a practical solution for monitoring inaccessible or dangerous areas. These systems offer real-time video feedback and flexible movement, overcoming the limitations of traditional static surveillance setups [3]. Advanced implementations also incorporate features such as motion detection, sensor integration, and alert systems, which enhance the overall performance and reliability of surveillance systems [4].

The use of wireless communication and sensor-based navigation improves the efficiency and safety surveillance robots in real-world scenarios. Such systems are capable of operating in low-light conditions and can be deployed for domestic, industrial, and security purposes, reducing the need for continuous and can be deployed for domestic, industrial, and security purposes, reducing the need for continuous human supervision[5]. This design is develop a low-cost, efficient, and portable surveillance robot using the ESP32 microcontroller. The system aims to provide real-time monitoring, remote control, and enhanced mobility, making it suitable for applications such as security surveillance, disaster management, industrial inspection, and military operations.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

The development of surveillance robots has gained significant attention in recent years due to the increasing need for intelligent monitoring systems. Several researchers have explored the integration of embedded systems, wireless communication, and robotics to design efficient surveillance solutions. A study presented by Dr. Nookala Venu focused on the development of an IoT-based surveillance robot using the ESP32-CAM module for border security applications. The system was designed to monitor restricted areas and detect intrusions in real time. The work emphasized reducing human involvement in high-risk zones while improving continuous monitoring efficiency [1].

P. R. Thulasi et al. proposed a web-controlled surveillance robot powered by the ESP32 microcontroller. The system enabled users to control the

robot through a web interface while receiving live video streaming. The study highlighted the effectiveness of wi-fi based communication in providing remote accessibility and ease of operation [2].

A surveillance system integrating ESP32-CAM with an Android-based control application was presented by multiple authors. This system allowed real-time video transition along with wireless control of the robot. The design was particularly suitable for monitoring hazardous or inaccessible environments and demonstrated a cost-effective approach to surveillance technology [3].

The research introduced a real-time video surveillance system using the ESP32-CAM module for IoT applications. The system incorporated features such as motion detection and alert notifications, enhancing its capability for smart monitoring. It also supported remote access through mobile and web platforms, making it applicable in both residential and industrial security systems[4]. The development of an advanced surveillance robot using ESP32-CAM and sensors for domestic applications. The system enabled real-time monitoring and was capable of operating even in low-light conditions. The research highlighted the importance of wireless communication and sensor integration in improving surveillance and reducing human effort[5].

A surveillance robotic car using the Esp32-CAM module was developed to overcome the limitations of static CCTV systems. The system provided mobility, real-time video transmission, and remote control capabilities. The study demonstrated how robotic surveillance systems can offer flexibility and adaptability in dynamic environments [6]. The ESP32 based surveillance systems provide an effective combination of low cost, wireless communication, and real-time monitoring. However, there is still scope for improvement in terms of system integration, mobility efficiency, and scalability. The proposed system aims to address these aspects by developing a compact and efficient surveillance robot with enhanced real-time performance and user control.

3. EXISTING METHOD

Traditional surveillance systems have been widely used for monitoring purposes in residential, commercial, and industrial environments. The most commonly

adopted method involves the use of fixed Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) cameras, which continuously capture and record video within a predefined area. Although these systems are effective for basic monitoring, they are limited by their fixed field of view and inability to cover dynamic or large-scale environments [6].

To overcome these limitations, several researchers have proposed surveillance systems based on wireless communication and embedded platforms. Early approaches involved the use of microcontrollers with external camera modules, where video data was transmitted to a monitoring station through wired or basic wireless networks. However, these systems often required complex hardware setups and lacked real-time remote accessibility [3].

With the advancement of Internet of Things (IoT) technologies, ESP32-based surveillance systems have been introduced to improve flexibility and performance. These systems utilize the ESP32-CAM module to capture and stream live video over Wi-Fi networks. Users can access the video feed through web interfaces or mobile applications, enabling remote monitoring capabilities [2]. Despite these improvements, many existing systems are still limited to stationary configurations, reducing their effectiveness in covering larger areas.

Some existing methods incorporate robotic platforms to introduce mobility into surveillance systems. These robots are typically controlled using wireless interfaces and can navigate through environment while transmitting live video. However, such systems may face challenges related to high cost, complex design, or limited integration of sensors for obstacle detection and autonomous navigation [5].

The advanced surveillance solutions have implemented features such as motion detection and alert notifications to enhance monitoring efficiency. While these systems improve responsiveness, they often increase system complexity and may require higher computational resources [4].

Existing methods have significantly contributed to the development of modern surveillance systems by integrating wireless communication, real-time video streaming, and basic mobility. However, there remains a need for a more compact, cost-effective, and fully integrated solution that combines mobility, real-time monitoring, and ease of control in a single platform.

4. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed system focuses on the design and implementation of a mobile surveillance robot using the ESP32 microcontroller, integrating wireless communication, real-time video streaming, and robotic movement. The methodology is structured to ensure efficient coordination between hardware components and software control for reliable surveillance operations. The system architecture consists of an ESP32 microcontroller as the central processing unit, a camera module for live video streaming, motor drivers for movement control, DC motors for mobility, and optional sensors for obstacle detection. The ESP32 is selected due to its built-in Wi-Fi capability, which enables seamless communication between the robot and the user interface without requiring additional communication modules [2].

The working of the system begins with the user sending control commands through a mobile application or web-based interface. These commands are transmitted over a wireless network and received by the ESP32 module. Based on the received input, the ESP32 processes the data and generates appropriate control signals to the motor driver. The motor drives the DC motors, allowing the robot to move in forward, backward, left, or right directions. Simultaneously, the camera module connected to the ESP32 captures real-time video and streams it to the user interface via Wi-Fi. This enables continuous monitoring of the robot's surroundings from a remote location. The real-time streaming capability enhances situational awareness and improves decision-making during surveillance operations [3].

To improve navigation and safety, sensors such as ultrasonic sensors can be integrated into the system. These sensors continuously detect obstacles in the robot's path and send feedback to the ESP32. Based on this input, the controller can either alert the user or automatically adjust the robot's movement to avoid collisions, thereby enhancing operational reliability [5]. The entire system is powered by a regulated power supply unit that ensures stable voltage for all components. Efficient power management is considered to support portability and long-duration operation. The compact design of the system allows it to operate in confined or hard-to-reach areas, making it suitable for various real-world applications. The proposed

methodology combines embedded systems, IoT-based communication, and robotics to develop a flexible and scalable surveillance solution. The system is designed to overcome the limitations of traditional static surveillance systems by providing mobility, remote accessibility, and real-time monitoring capabilities [6].

BLOCK DIAGRAM & WORKING PRINCIPLE

BLOCK DIAGRAM:

Fig 4.1: BLOCK DIAGRAM

Working Principle:

The proposed surveillance robot is based on the coordination between the ESP32 microcontroller, camera module, motor driver, and communication interface. The system operates through wireless communication, enabling real-time control and monitoring. The process begins when the user sends a control commands through a mobile application or a web-based interface. These commands are transmitted over a Wi-Fi network and received by the ESP32 microcontroller, which acts as the central control unit of the system upon receiving the commands the ESP32 processes theinput and determines the required action.

Based on the user’s instructions, the ESP32 generates appropriate control signals and sends them to the motor driver module. The motor driver acts as an interface between the sends them to the motor driver module. The motor driver acts as an interface between the microcontroller and the DC motors by amplifying the signals. As a result, the motors rotate accordingly, allowing the robot to move in different directions such as forward, backward, left, or right. At the same time, the camera module connected to the ESP32 continuously captures live video of the robot’s surroundings. This video data is processed and transmitted wirelessly through the ESP32’s built in wi-fi module to the user interface. The

user can view the real time video stream, which enables effective monitoring and control of the robot from a remote location.

If sensors such as ultrasonic sensors are integrated into the system, they continuously monitor the environment for obstacles. When an obstacle is detected, the sensor sends feedback to the ESP32. Based on this information, the system can either alert the user or adjust the movement of the robot to prevent collisions. This enhances the safety and reliability of the system during operation. The entire system is powered by a regulated power supply that ensures stable voltages for all components. The efficient interaction between hardware and software enables the robot to perform surveillance tasks smoothly and in real time. The system works as an integrated unit where wireless communication, real-time video streaming, and controlled movement are combined to achieve an effective and flexible surveillance solution.

5. RESULTS AND OUTCOMES

The developed surveillance robot using the ESP32 microcontroller was successfully designed and implemented to perform real-time monitoring and remote navigation. The system demonstrated reliable wireless communication between the user interface and the robot through Wi-Fi, enabling smooth and responsive control[2].

During experimental testing, robot responded accurately to user commands received from the mobile or web interface. The motor driver and Dc motor operated efficiently, allowing controlled movement in multiple directions such as forward, backward, left, and right. This confirms the effectiveness of ESP32-based control systems in real-time robotic applications[3].

Fig 5.1 : OUTPUT-1

Fig 5.2: OUTPUT-2

The camera module integrated with the system provided continuous real-time video streaming with minimal latency. The video feed was clear and consistent, allowing users to monitor the environment effectively from a remote location. This validates the capability of ESP32-CAM based systems for live surveillance applications[4].

When a sensor were incorporated into the system, the robot was able to detect obstacles and respond accordingly. The feedback mechanism improved navigation and reduced the chances of collision, thereby enhancing system safety and reliability. Similar approaches have been shown to improve monitoring efficiency in intelligent surveilnace systems [5].

The system also exhibited stable performance with low power consumption, making it suitable for portable and long-duration applications. The integration of wireless communication, real-time streaming, and robotic mobility demonstrates a significant improvement over traditional static surveillance systems [6].

The results confirm that the proposed system is a cost-effective and efficient solution for real-time surveillance. It successfully combines mobility, remote accessibility, and continuous monitoring, aligning with recent advancements in IoT-based robotic surveillance technologies.

6. CONCLUSION

In this work, a mobile surveillance robot based on the ESP32 microcontroller has been successfully designed and implemented to address the limitations of conventional surveillance systems. Unlike traditional fixed monitoring solutions, the proposed system offers mobility, real-time video streaming, and remote accessibility, making it suitable for dynamic and large-scale environments.

The integration of the ESP32 with a camera module enables efficient wireless communication and live video

transmission, allowing users to monitor surroundings from remote locations. The use of motor drivers and DC motors ensures smooth and responsive movement of the robot, while the optional integration of sensors enhances navigation and operational safety. These features collectively demonstrate the effectiveness of combining embedded systems, IoT technology, and robotics into a single surveillance platform [2][3].

The system has been shown to operate reliably with low power consumption and minimal hardware complexity, making it cost-effective solution for various applications. Compared to existing methods, the proposed approach improves flexibility and coverage while maintaining simplicity in design and implementation [6].

The project highlights the potential of ESP32-based systems in developing smart and scalable surveillance solutions. The modular nature of the design allows future enhancements such as artificial intelligence, automation, and advanced sensing techniques to be incorporated for improved performance and decision-making capabilities [4][5].

The developed surveillance robot provides an efficient, portable, and adaptable solution for modern monitoring requirements. It demonstrates how emerging technologies can be effectively utilized to enhance safety, security, and remote observation in real-world scenarios

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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